

GEARBOX CASINGS OF FIBRE-REINFORCED PLASTIC FOR AERO
ENGINES

A. Rossmann / W. Feist / H. Zech

Motoren-und Turbinen-Union GmbH
Dachauer Str. 665

8000 München 50

External gearbox casings for aero engines have, so far, usually been cast from light-metal alloys, which, however, have some disadvantages with regard to operating behaviour and maintainability. Fibre-reinforced composite materials proffer themselves as alternatives. Therefore, at MTU München, the manufacturing technique and design principles for external gearbox casings made from C-fibre reinforced epoxide have been worked out in the course of several years of development work financed by the Federal German Ministry of Defence (I), and a typical component has been successfully manufactured and tried out under service-like conditions. The results of trials are so positive that application of the acquired technology to various engine components is feasible.

Introduction

Outside engine technology circles, it is largely unknown that gas turbine engines usually have several gearboxes making up a percentage of the weight which cannot be ignored. A distinction can be made between internal gearboxes integrated in the load-bearing structure of the engine and external gearboxes which are attached outside on the casing (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Typical external engine casing selected for the test model, with the location on the compressor casing.

External gearboxes are usually driven from the engine rotor via internal gearing and transmit power to built-on accessories such as control units, pumps and generators. The casings of such gearboxes are sand castings made from light-metal alloys, aluminium and magnesium alloys being used for this purpose. Although the specific strengths of Al- and Mg- alloys are similar, design considerations prevent these strengths from being fully utilised, so that specific weights seem a more suitable criterion. Al-alloys are heavier ($\gamma \approx 2.9 \text{ g/cm}^3$) than Mg-alloys ($\gamma \approx 1.9 \text{ g/cm}^3$), but the latter are in turn extremely susceptible to corrosion. As C-fibre reinforced epoxy resins combine the advantages of freedom from corrosion and low specific weight ($\gamma \approx 1.4 \text{ g/cm}^3$), they proffered themselves as material for gearbox casings. It was intended to find out whether these advantages could be applied to an actual component. In the course of these investigations, a suitable manufacturing technique had to be developed and tested, and design principles for gearbox casings incorporating fibre technology had to be worked out.

Description of the component to be replaced

A casing from a GE J-79 11A engine external gearbox was selected as a model for development work. This casing is made from a Mg casting alloy (AMS 4434) and has the typical characteristics of such gearbox casings for engines. It has a longish, shallow configuration (overall length approx. 500 mm and a weight in light metal of approx. 4 kg) and consists of two parts, a somewhat deeper casing proper and a relatively shallow cover (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Cover for the gearbox casing.

There are several screws which hold the cover to the casing. Inside the casing there is a train of 5 gearwheels with an input speed of 3750 r.p.m. and capable of transmitting a power of 25 kW. The gearwheels run in antifricition bearings in the gearbox. Oil jet nozzles, likewise secured to the casing walls, are used to lubricate and cool the gearwheels and bearings. The fuel pump and engine generator, amongst other items, are fitted on to the gearbox. Normally, the component temperature is $<70^{\circ}\text{C}$; local peak temperatures $<120^{\circ}\text{C}$ can occur temporarily (minutes). Starting-up and shutting-down operations involve both mechanical and thermal load changes, a time between overhauls of approx. 1000 hours involving roughly as many load cycles. The inside of the component is pressurised with Mil 23699 engine oil, the maximum internal pressure being 1.8 bar. On its outside, the casing is exposed to atmospheric conditions, corrosion occurring during periods of non-use, particularly in service areas near the sea. Significant dynamic loadings can occur through accessories being out of balance, vibrations of the engine, pressure surges of the pumps and acceleration forces from flight manoeuvres.

In addition to the already mentioned susceptibility to corrosion, cast magnesium material (important material data: see Table 1) has other disadvantages and failings, inter alia:

- it is easily affected by paint stripping baths prior to crack inspection during overhaul. This severely limits the number of overhauls which are possible.
- Low fatigue strength may lead to rupture of mountings and accessory attachments.
- inevitable porosity and oxide inclusions which diminish strength.
- high thermal expansion affects the centre distance between gearwheels and thus operating behaviour.

There are, moreover, the general disadvantages which metallic materials have compared with fibre materials, such as:

- little intrinsic damping and thus relative proneness to vibration and considerable radiation of gear-wheel noise.
- relatively expensive machining of the casting blank.

Selection of manufacturing process and material

Preliminary tests had shown that, owing to the complicated shape in three dimensions of the casing and the varying wall thickness, manufacturing processes such as laminating or filament winding cannot compete in manufacturing price with the metallic components, or that insufficient consistency can be expected in production. As a magnesium casting with relatively low strength but favourable specific weight was to be replaced, a non-directional fibre compression moulding material was selected as an alternative material.

The material involved is a pre-impregnated form of compression moulding material with a thermosetting epoxy-resin matrix and approximately 35% by weight of non-directional C-fibres about 13 mm long as reinforcement (see Table 1).

Table 1. Properties of materials

Composition of material and associated data	AMS 4434						C-fibre (Grafil NF) Fibre Ø 8 µm	Matrix Epoxy resin (corresponding to Araldit 556 Hardener 975)	Compression moulding material	
	Al	Zn	Mn	Si	Cu	Remainder			without pretreatment	with pretreatment
	8,3 9,7	1,6 2,4	0,1 —	— 0,3	— 0,1	Mg			35% by weight C-fibre approx. 13 mm long, nondirectional, + epoxy resin	
Breaking strength [N/mm ² ¹⁾]	>120						200	50 - 80	≈ 150	≈ 300
Yield point [N/mm ²]	>95									
Elongation at rupture [%]	> 0,75 (for 50 mm gauge length)						1,1% (elastic)	≈ 2,5% (elastic)		
Fatigue strength [N/mm ²]	±70 (for 10 ⁷ reversed bending stress cycles)									
Module of elasticity [N/mm ²] (RT)	42,000						180,000	3,000	30,000	30,000
Mean coefficient of expansion at operating temperature [°C ⁻¹]	25.10 ⁻⁶						(-1-0).10 ⁻⁶	≈ 25.10 ⁻⁶	≈ 14.10 ⁻⁶	≈ 14.10 ⁻⁶
Density [g/cm ³]	1,9						1,7	1,2	≈ 1,4	≈ 1,4

¹⁾ N/mm² = 145 psi

This material is supplied as a pre-impregnated moulding material and, after being given special preliminary treatment, is shaped in a moulding die at approx. 160°C and 50 bar pressure and hardened. Test bars taken from the components were found to have strength properties at least equal to those of the magnesium casting (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3: Comparison of typical properties of gearbox materials

Advantages of this process and material over the magnesium casting are:

- freedom from corrosion
- good vibration characteristics, high damping, little radiation of noise
- approx. 30% weight saving for same volume
- inexpensive manufacturing process for the finished component
- relatively low thermal expansion ($14 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$).

Owing to the press mould costs, manufacture of a metal mould with the finished-part shape, including screwing and fastening elements such as would be needed for efficient production, was dispensed with. Instead, "plastic dies" (Fig. 4) with only the outer and inner contour of the casing were made; the receptacles for the bearings and such items as stay bolts were fitted subsequently.

Fig. 4: Female die Male die
Heatable press tool made of plastic.

Testing of the casing

The aim of the investigations was to verify the serviceability of the component and to work out, at the same time, design principles for casings and similar components in which this fibre technology is used. Investigations were concentrated on

- Fastening of anti-friction bearings and gaskets (Fig. 5)

- Screwing together and sealing of the casing halves
- Fastening of built-on accessories (e.g., generators, (Fig.6)

In part, recourse was had, for the first attempts at a solution, to those techniques which had been proven in the case of magnesium casings, most of which techniques had to be modified, however, to the special requirements of the fibre material.

Fig. 5: Fibre-reinforced gearbox casing with built-in anti-friction bearing shells.

Fig. 6: Fibre-reinforced gearbox casing with stay bolts for accessories.

Rig tests

The casing made from C-fibre reinforced material was mounted on a torsion test stand (Fig. 7) together with two gearboxes as fitted to the J79. There were two self-contained torque systems providing 26,5 kW and 3 kW, corresponding to 75 Nm and 8 Nm torque respectively on the torque shafts and to the nominal ratings.

Fig. 7: 4-shaft torsional test loading stand for gearbox.
Conventional gearbox with cast magnesium casing in the centre.

Prior to assembly, all bearings were equipped with thermocouples between the bearing shells and the plastic material in order to monitor the bearing temperature, to avoid overheating and provide timely indication of any bearing damage. The tests were carried out in cycles, i.e., they were carried on each time until the temperature was balanced at 80 - 90 °C. Then, the casing was allowed to cool down to nearly room temperature, in order to superimpose thermal load cycles on the mechanical load cycles.

The oil used for lubrication and cooling was the synthetic oil MIL 7808 used also in the gearbox fitted to the engine.

Results from running tests

After the running tests, the gearwheels showed good bearing patterns which were uniform over the facewidth. This indicates satisfactory running without appreciable distortion of the casings.

The threaded connections of both casing halves, for which at first helicoil inserts were used, proved to be unsatisfactory. The static friction of these inserts in the composite material is so low that they are partly pulled out when the bolts are removed and are damaged as a result (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8: Helicoil insert partly pulled out when the gearbox was stripped.

Here, other solutions had to be sought.

In addition, the lugs in the flange proved too weak for screwing together the casing halves. Some of them burst apart, when the bolts were tightened (Fig. 9). This deficiency can also be corrected by purposive design changes.

Even tests in which the power transmitted by the gearbox was increased up to a critical value - determined by the load carrying capacity of the oil used - did not lead to a casing failure but only to damage to the ball bearings, which are not designed for such high loads.

Fig. 9: Lug which has burst apart.

Test with various types of thread fastening in
C-fibre reinforced material

As already mentioned above, the helicoil thread inserts used, which have proven their serviceability in light metals, were not found to be satisfactory, since they could not be removed without damage. In addition, use of these inserts is not an economic proposition, since drilling and thread tapping is also required. An alternative for compression-moulded components is the possibility of pressing-in thread inserts during manufacture of the casing.

In order to assess the strength of various pressed-in and cemented-in thread inserts and - for the purpose of comparison - of conventional helicoil inserts, comparative tests were carried out on test specimens in a test rig (Fig. 10) adapted for the purpose. In these tests, cyclic loads were superimposed on static pre-loads, such as are typical for bolted connections.

Fig. 10: Rig for testing the fatigue strength of thread inserts.

If, instead of damage to the thread insert, the bolt fractured, the connection was considered satisfactory.

Summary of the test results:

- A reliable, but expensive connection is provided by screwed-in and additionally cemented-in helicoil inserts, with the adhesive serving as an anti-rotation lock.
- In most cases, cemented-in threaded sleeves were pulled out merely under average static load (Fig. 11). A satisfactory connection was only achieved when the sleeve was sunk so deep into the hole as to provide sufficient support from the material above to prevent break-outs from the rim of the hole (Fig. 12).

Fig. 11: Cemented-in threaded sleeve which has been pulled out.

Fig. 12: Sunk-in cemented threaded sleeve with fatigue-fractured bolt.

Pressed-in threaded sleeves, however, proved to be very unsatisfactory. In all cases, the sleeves were pulled out of the test specimens as soon as the static load was applied, the test specimen breaking off in layers with the fractures starting from the sleeves (Fig. 13).

Fig. 13: Cemented-in threaded sleeve which has broken apart.

In this case, the behaviour of C-fibre-reinforced compression moulding material differs from that of glass-fibre-reinforced material tested in the same way. For glass-fibre material, pressing-in of threaded inserts represents the state of the art. It is suspected that the failure of C-fibre-reinforced material is caused by high notch sensitivity and brittleness.

It can, however, be assumed that pressed-in recessed threaded sleeves will sooner meet the requirements than recessed cemented-in sleeves.

Dynamic tests with simulated out-of-balance accessory

A major factor for evaluating a casing material is the fatigue strength of the component made from this material. Fatigue resistance is required, for instance, if flanged-on accessories, such as generators or pumps, exert a continuous stress on the mounting flange through a rotary moment resulting from out-of-balance rotors.

In order to obtain information on the fatigue strength, a comparative test was carried out on a casing half made from C-fibre reinforced material and on an original casing in cast magnesium.

For this purpose, the casing half was clamped flush on an angle plate. A mechanical vibration exciter manufactured by Schenck was mounted with a flange on the casing flange to which, in the J79 production gearbox, a hydraulic pump is attached, the exciter being driven by a flexible shaft. (Fig. 14).

Fig. 14: Setup for dynamic tests with simulated out-of-balance accessory.

The rotary bending moment applied can be controlled by the speed and was set to 6600 N·cm.

During testing of the magnesium casing, fracture occurred in a side wall after $1,6 \times 10^7$ load cycles (Fig. 15). The high number of load cycles shows that the load applied was only insignificantly higher than the fatigue strength at this critical site.

Fig. 15: Crack in magnesium casing after 1.6×10^7 load cycles, made visible by inspection with penetrant.

The casing in C-fibre reinforced material failed after $2 \cdot 10^6$ load cycles at the same amplitude, but the fracture occurred at another site (Fig. 16). The fracture runs through the bottom of a hole for one of the flange mounting threads. It is possible that there were already internal cracks prior to testing, the cracks being caused by screwing in the moulding threads of the stay bolts. Such a type of fastening for the bolts is the worst imaginable one for C-fibre reinforced material because of the latter's brittleness. In the future, threaded inserts should be pressed in at this site during manufacture of the casing. In addition, the site concerned is - with regard to stability of shape - really predestined to fracture, since the force is directly transmitted from the stay bolt via the casing reinforcement to the bolt in the mounting flange, and the casing is not so elastic as in the case of the other stay bolts. This shows again that in the design of components more consideration must be given to the properties of materials.

Altogether, the test has shown that, with regard to component-related fatigue strength, the properties of the casing in C-fibre reinforced material in its present form are, over the range tested, not significantly worse than those of the cast magnesium casing. It is probable that the final version will have better properties than the magnesium casing, provided that the threaded parts are moulded in during manufacture of the casing.

Fig. 16: Crack in C-fibre reinforced material after 2×10^6 load cycles, made visible by inspection with penetrant.

Prospects

Further activities are now called for to match the fitting of the gearbox to the engine to the fibre-technology requirements. Prior to a run on the engine, however, the fatigue strengths of the overall set-up required to conform with the relevant regulations on accessories for aero engines and to match the expected dynamic operating loads must be verified on a vibration test stand. Investigations on the long-time behaviour of the fibre material under external influences such as engine oil, salt-bearing air at local operating temperatures on the casing up to 160°C and thermal cycles are already underway or will follow.

Unidirectional short-fibre pre-impregnated materials (II) developed by MBB München in recent times are significantly expanding the potential applications for fibre materials. The extreme strengths, approaching those of filament windings, achievable in this way make the manufacture of blading and rotor parts, besides gas-conducting casing parts, by pressing technique now seem conceivable.

From the results to date of investigations, it can already be seen that vast interesting possibilities exist for C-fibre epoxide compression moulding materials in engine building and justify further intensive activities, so that we can reckon with their use in production for suitable engine components in the years immediately ahead.

References

- (I) Aviation Advanced Technology Programme, MTU task 202.2,3,4, Final Reports 1974, 1975, 1976 W.D. Feist, H. Zech.
- (II) MBB WF-Information 2/77 BT 007, Pp 13-19.